

How to improve career construction for civil engineering students?

Ida Nugroho Saputro^{1,2}, Soenarto¹, Herminarto Sofyan¹

¹Postgraduate Program of Technology and Vocational Education, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Building Engineering Education, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Career construction has received significant attention from Scholars in various countries. Strengthening career construction is believed to help individuals get closer to students' career choices according to their field of expertise. However, studies on establishing career construction for vocational students involving instructional quality factors, social support, and career self-efficacy have not been found. Therefore, this study examines the antecedent factors that shape career construction by involving instructional quality, social support, and career self-efficacy of vocational high school students. This study proves that career construction is directly influenced positively by career self-efficacy. The instructional quality and social support, however, had no direct impact on how a profession was constructed. Another finding, career self-efficacy is directly influenced positively by the quality of instructional and social support of students. Finally, this study reveals that career self-efficacy acts as a mediator to mediate the effect of instructional quality and social support on the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students. The findings of this study have significant ramifications for practitioners in vocational education who are creating strengthening programs or career development for vocational students.

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Corresponding Author:

Ida Nugroho Saputro

Building Engineering Education, Universitas Sebelas Maret

Jebres, Surakarta, Central Java 57126, Indonesia

Email: idanugroho@staff.uns.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Career development and preparation for vocational education graduates is a critical issue to describe the extent to which the success of vocational education in shaping career readiness for students. The primary reason is that philosophically, vocational education is education that prepares students to be skilled in specific skills. So, it is natural that vocational education graduates have high expectations of job acquisition or career success after graduation. In addition, getting a job following the competencies possessed is hope for every vocational education graduate. Thus, information about vocational education graduates' career construction is essential to determine their career readiness. According to Savickas [1], the study of career construction has become increasingly prominent in the study of career psychology. Many scholars give essential attention to career construction development [2]–[6]. Career construction theory is a key idea for individual career development, notably in assisting clients in directing their career choices [5], [7]–[10]. Although much literature examines career construction, there are still limited studies that discuss how career construction is formed among engineering students.

Career construction theory is a career creation model that connects the characteristics of adaptivity, adaptability, adaptation, and adaption to describe the career construction process throughout the course of a person's lifetime [5]. The adaptation model of career construction thus describes the interaction of constant personal characteristics, psychological capacities, career behaviors, and career outcomes and assumes that adequate career behaviors (adapting responses) facilitated by psychological capacity (adaptability resources) and personal characteristics will lead to the best career outcomes (adaptation results) (adaptive readiness). The career construction assessment model, in accordance with Savickas *et al.* [5], crystallizes a vocational self-concept, investigates knowledge about professions, chooses to commit to an occupational choice, and becomes ready to carry out that choice. In principle, career construction theory explains how individuals assimilate their vocational self-concept to their job roles [11]. Because personal demands and societal expectations are successfully integrated, people who are successful in their occupations may adjust in a sustainable way [11], [12]. Furthermore, individuals who have good adaptation will be able to control their careers adaptively by optimizing their psychosocial resources.

In this context, vocational education graduates, especially vocational high school students, orientation toward career success in their respective fields of expertise. The main resources for preparing individuals for career preparedness are learning opportunities and professional internships. After graduation, vocational graduates should have good career readiness, especially in careers following their vocational education choices. However, unfortunately, previous studies found gaps between theory and findings in the field. One of them, a study conducted by Indana [13], revealed that most (90%) graduates of vocational high schools in Trenggalek, Indonesia did not work in the field of education. However, the current condition of the suitability of career choice with education is no longer critical. Workers are encouraged to be able to adapt to all of the needs of the workplace due to changes in the requirements for credentials in the workplace. The hope is that vocational high school graduates must have control over their careers in the world of work through career construction that has been established at school.

Previous researchers found that instructors' professional choices had an impact on the effectiveness of their instruction [8], [14]–[16]. The quality of education or teaching carried out by teachers encourages the strength of students' career plans. Students' learning experiences in schools play an essential role in providing maturity in students' career choices [17]. Role collaboration between learning experiences and personal and contextual aspects could strengthen one's career choice [17]. In addition, the scholars revealed that the quality of teaching encourages the maturity of students to choose their future career plans [18]–[20]. Another aspect that has received much attention from scholars regarding career studies is social support [17], [21]. Support from influential people such as family and friends significantly influences one's career [21]–[25]. Meanwhile, other studies also show that self-efficacy determines the construction of a person's career choice toward the chosen career [4], [14], [21], [26]. As a result, we think that self-efficacy, social support, and high-quality instruction are essential for preparing vocational students for their future careers.

The significance of developing career construction has been studied in several research. Theoretical and practical gaps persist, particularly in regard to how instructional quality, social support, and self-efficacy impact vocational students' career development in the area of mechanical engineering specialization. As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the structural career creation model using as its antecedents the instructional quality, social support, and self-efficacy of vocational high school students in the field of mechanical engineering. As a consequence, the goal of this study is to analyze the structural career construction model by using the instructional quality, social support, and self-efficacy of vocational high school students in the area of mechanical engineering as its antecedents. This study aims to investigate the measurement model of vocational high school students' career construction, instructional quality, social support, and self-efficacy; to investigate the effect of instructional quality, social support, and self-efficacy on vocational students' career construction; and to analyze the mediating function of self-efficacy on the influence of instructional quality and social support on vocational students' career construction.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Career construction and instructional quality

According to the career formation idea, professional growth is more like environmental adaptability than simple maturation. A hypothesis concerning career growth is called the career creation theory. Many academics today focus on career development in their research [2], [4], [27], [28]. The hypothesis is based on the developmental, differential, and dynamic views of occupational behavior [5], [11]. In perspective, this theory develops to explain how someone adapts their self-concept to their career choices.

In many cases, career construction is often linked to career adaptability [1] and not yet specified how other vital components shape career construction. This hypothesis contributes to the research on the process of proactive and adaptive career progression through time. According to Savickas *et al.* [5], the link

between the characteristics of adaptivity, adaptability, adapting, and adaptation may be used to explain career formation. In conclusion, this career architecture demonstrates how having the right professional behavior backed by the right psychological skills and personality attributes will lead to the best career outcomes.

A career creation questionnaire designed for counselors and researchers has been evaluated by Savickas *et al.* [5] to determine its reliability. The goal of the inventory research is to quantify the adaptive responses—which include job-related thought and behavior—involved in making career decisions. Career development for vocational high school students has a strategic role, especially in preparing vocational high school graduates to have strong career choices. Looking at the basic theory of vocational education, vocational education aims to prepare skilled individuals for certain types of work [29]. That is, vocational high school graduates must have a career choice following their field of expertise. Career construction studies are often associated with career choices or career adaptability [5]. Many factors impact career development in the context of schooling. One of them is the instructional quality of the instructor when teaching in the classroom. The ability of teachers to mobilize students' confidence in their vocational abilities can strengthen students' career choices [25]. This means that career self-efficacy or students' beliefs about their career abilities also contribute to their increased perceptions of career choices. Other scholars also revealed that the quality of teacher teaching has a positive impact on students' career formation [15], [16]. The vocational-related learning experience provided by the teacher to students will instill experience about the perception of the vocational career they will choose as previous studies stated that students' learning experiences in schools play an essential role in providing maturity of students' career choices [17].

This literature review provides an essential point that instructional quality is an essential factor when teachers will shape the career construction of vocational students. Thus, teachers must strive to develop and improve their instructional quality to direct students closer to their career choice after graduation. According to prior research, career building may be assessed by determining how far a person perceives their ability to develop a professional self-concept, learn about various occupations, make a decision about which occupation to pursue, and be ready to pursue that option [5]. Thus, the hypothesis of the study: Instructional quality has a positive influence on the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students (H1); and instructional quality has a positive influence on career self-efficacy of civil engineering high school students (H2).

2.2. The role of social support: career self-efficacy and career construction

According to theory, social support is acquired by resources made available by others [30]. Social support may come from a variety of places, including material support, approval support, self-esteem support, and belonging support [31]. Social support, in the context of professional development, refers to the assistance received in the form of money or emotional support during their socialization process. As a result, it will encourage positive thinking, reason, and optimism in their hopes for professional advancement [32]. Positive sources of social support help individuals to believe in their abilities, especially regarding their career abilities [33]. Previous studies have also revealed that social support provides an impetus for increasing individual career adaptability [25]. Adolescents are more upbeat about their professional growth when their parents are supportive and supportive [34]. Parental and teacher support is positively connected to career optimism, and this direct association is entirely mediated by self-efficacy in making professional decisions [35]. Social support also assists students in making better professional selections and encourages them to explore and plan their future with optimism [36]. As a result, we believe that social support increases students' career self-efficacy and growth. According to the explanation, the proposed hypothesis: Social support has a positive influence on the formation of career construction for civil engineering vocational high school students (H3); and social support has a positive influence on the career self-efficacy of civil engineering vocational high school students (H4).

2.3. The mediating role of career self-efficacy

Career development studies have involved many important self-efficacy factors, especially regarding individual beliefs about their career abilities [35], [37], [38]. Career self-efficacy, according to Taylor and Betz [39], is the belief that a person has in their capacity to carry out career-related activities. High levels of career self-efficacy assist people to overcome career obstacles and have a beneficial influence on decision-making attitudes and behavior [40]. The most significant element affecting students' decision to pursue a job is their level of career self-efficacy [41]. Furthermore, professional self-efficacy moderates the influence of educational quality and social support on occupational flexibility [25]. Self-efficacy is mentioned in other pertinent research as a mediator between social support and career flexibility [42]. This literature review indicates that building career self-efficacy for civil engineering vocational high school students is very important to help them strengthen their career construction. Thus, career self-efficacy is thought to operate as a moderator of the impact of instructional quality and social support on the career development of civil engineering vocational high school students. Hence, the proposed hypothesis: Career

self-efficacy significantly affects the career construction of civil engineering high school students (H5); Career self-efficacy significantly mediates the effect of instructional quality on career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students (H6); and Career self-efficacy significantly mediates the effect of social support on the career construction of civil engineering high school students (H7).

Building a database from the previous literature, it can be highlighted that career construction is an essential aspect for civil engineering vocational high school students while still paying attention to other essential factors that play a role in strengthening career construction. These essential components include the caliber of the training, social support, and professional self-efficacy. As a result, Figure 1 shows conceptual model development.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Students from Surakarta's state vocational high school for civil engineering competence participated in this study. Online surveys were issued at random to vocational students with specialization in civil engineering in Surakarta, Indonesia. Out of the 400 questionnaires distributed, 255 were sent for analysis. There were 190 (74.5%) male students and 65 (25.5%) female students among those who responded. In the online questionnaire, students assessed their perceptions of instructional quality, social support, career self-efficacy, and career construction on themselves. The development of this study questionnaire used a reference to previous studies consisting of an instructional quality questionnaire [43], [44], social support [45], self-efficacy career [46], and career construction [5]. All instruments use a Likert scale with five alternative answers (strongly agree=5, agree=4, somewhat agree=3, disagree=2, strongly disagree=1).

Partially least squares (PLS) analysis of structural equation modeling (SEM) was utilized in this study to evaluate the relationship between variable constructs, including both exogenous and endogenous variables, while also accounting for measurement errors [47]. We used the SmartPLS 3.0 software to test the hypotheses of this study. PLS is a variant-based SEM analysis that evaluates both the structural and measurement models at once [48]. The outer model (measurement model) in the PLS-SEM analysis aims to test the reliability of the questionnaire. The loading factor parameter and the average variance extracted (AVE) value are used in the outer model testing criterion. The criterion employed include a loading factor parameter value more than 0.7 and an AVE value greater than 0.5 [49]. Meanwhile, hypothesis testing employs the inner model testing criterion, with the hypothesis accepted if the p-value is less than 0.05 and rejected if it is more than 0.05.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Validity and reliability test

Testing the questionnaire's reliability and validity comes first in the analysis of this study. PLS-SEM was used to assess the questionnaire's validity and reliability on vocational students' views of teaching quality, social support, career self-efficacy, and career construction in the field of civil engineering (outer

model). Confirmatory factor analysis is used in this test on the outer SEM model created with SmartPLS (v.3.2.9). Figure 2 displays the findings of the first running model.

The outcomes of the outer model analysis undertaken to evaluate the validity and reliability of the surveys on instructional quality, social support, career self-efficacy, and career creation are shown in Figure 2 and Table 1. The results of the outer model analysis on all variables show valid (.779~.940) and reliable results (.796~.944). In the validity test, each indicator shows a loading factor value above 0.70. Each indicator on each variable can explain the latent variables in this study. In addition, reliability testing also shows an AVE value above 0.50. This finding means that the questionnaire used in this study is accurate for measuring student perceptions of instructional quality, social support, career self-efficacy, and career construction for civil engineering vocational high school students.

Figure 2. Path diagram of career construction antecedent factors for vocational high school students

Table 1. Questionnaire validity and reliability

Variables (N)	Validity	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	AVE
Instructional quality	.799 ~ .926	.897	.929	.766
Social support	.815 ~ .874	.796	.879	.709
Career self-efficacy	.779 ~ .891	.919	.939	.756
Career construction	.912 ~ .940	.944	.960	.857

4.2. Hypothesis testing using SEM analysis

The path coefficient test is used in this study to assess the hypothesis. However, before evaluating the hypothesis, the fit model must be tested using the goodness of fit test. The normed fit index (NFI=0.823) and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR=0.70) values are good and match the model fit criteria, according to the goodness of fit criterion test using SmartPLS-SEM. The model is said to be fit if it has an NFI value above 0.8 and an SRMR below 0.08 [50]. Furthermore, the hypothesis testing analysis can be done using the bootstrapping test method on smartPLS 3.2.9. The Bootstrapping method is used to test the significance of each chosen hypothesis. This study used 1000 bootstrap samples with a 95% confidence level. The results of this study's hypothesis testing are shown in Table 2.

In Table 2, it is known that the first hypothesis testing obtained a p-value of 0.684. If the p-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted (p 0.05). Thus, the first hypothesis is not accepted and means that instructional quality does not affect the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students. Meanwhile, instructional quality significantly affected students' career self-efficacy (the second hypothesis was accepted, p<0.05). Findings related to the insignificant effect were also shown on the effect of social support on career construction. The significance value or p-values is 0.255, meaning that p>0.05, and the third hypothesis is rejected. Testing the fourth hypothesis shows the acquisition of p-values of 0.002,

meaning that $p < 0.05$, and the fourth hypothesis is accepted. Social support has a considerable impact on civil engineering vocational high school students' career self-efficacy. Furthermore, other findings related to the direct effect also show that career self-efficacy significantly influences the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students. This is because the acquisition of p -values is 0.000, meaning that the fifth hypothesis is accepted.

Table 2. Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	T Statistic	P-Values
Instructional quality → Career construction	0.407	0.684
Instructional quality → Career self-efficacy	2.721	0.007
Social support → Career construction	1.139	0.255
Social support → Career self-efficacy	3.040	0.002
Career self-efficacy → Career construction	20.689	0.000
Instructional Quality → Career self-efficacy → Career construction	2.718	0.007
Social support → Career self-efficacy → Career construction	2.939	0.003

In testing the indirect effect of this study using the SmartPLS-SEM bootstrapping method. The sixth hypothesis test revealed p -values of 0.007 for the mediation test of career self-efficacy on the impact of instructional quality on career creation, indicating that the hypothesis was accepted. This finding suggests that career self-efficacy significantly moderates the influence of instructional quality on career development among high school students majoring in civil engineering. Moreover finally, testing the role of mediation was also carried out on the seventh hypothesis test. The mediation test yielded p -values of 0.003 ($p = 0.05$), indicating that career self-efficacy significantly moderated the influence of social support on the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students.

5. DISCUSSION

Career development for vocational students is an essential aspect of vocational education. This is because vocational education has characteristics of an educational institution that prepares prospective workers in certain areas of expertise. Strengthening the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students helps strengthen students' career plans when they graduate. The purpose of this research is to better understand the factors that encourage high school students to career construction in civil engineering. Instructional quality, social support, and career self-efficacy are among these characteristics. This study also investigates the role of professional self-efficacy in mitigating the effects of educational quality and social support on career advancement.

The findings showed that the sole factor significantly and favorably affecting how high school students majoring in civil engineering build their careers is career self-efficacy. While this was going on, other elements like the caliber of the education and social support had little to no impact on how the students in the civil engineering vocational high schools built their careers. This conclusion is pertinent to earlier research that shown professional self-efficacy had a direct impact on polytechnic students' capacity to modify their careers [25]. In a similar context related to career decisions, career self-efficacy is crucial to encourage individuals to make career choices. The ability to overcome career barriers increases with an individual's level of career self-efficacy [40]. Students' confidence in their job-related skills, such as self-evaluation, occupational knowledge, goal selection, planning, and problem-solving, improves the quality of their career construction. In order to increase their future profession options, students must be aware of their strengths or potential and be able to channel it. Additionally, their confidence in their capacity to deal with issues linked to their jobs enhances the foundation they have built for their careers. Students at civil engineering vocational high schools must complete a learning program that includes components of career self-efficacy such as self-evaluation, occupational information, goal selection, planning, and problem-solving.

Another conclusion is that students at vocational high schools for civil engineering do not directly benefit from improving career construction due to instructional quality. This study's findings are similar with previous research, which found no clear association between teaching quality and career flexibility [25]. These findings differ theoretically; the quality of teaching has an important influence on the formation of students' careers [15]. Good teaching quality will provide a positive learning experience, significantly strengthening students' careers. Lent and Brown [17] reveal that the vocational-related learning experiences provided by teachers to students will instill experiences about the perception of the vocational career they will choose. This means that the aspects of instructional quality consisting of motivation, understandable news, student involvement, and learning context have not been able to encourage strengthened career

construction. The effectiveness of this instruction directly affects how strongly vocational students feel they can succeed in their chosen careers. Subsequently, it influences the career construction of vocational students—the better the teacher's instructional quality, the stronger students' confidence in their career abilities. Furthermore, the strength of self-efficacy related to their careers will encourage the strengthening of crystallizing vocational self-concepts, exploring occupations, making decisions, and preparing for the careers of civil engineering vocational high school students.

Similar results on the influence of social support on career development were also demonstrated. The study's findings demonstrate that social support has no direct influence on how students at civil engineering vocational high school build their careers. On the other hand, social support has an indirect impact on career development through students at the civil engineering vocational high school's perception of their own professional effectiveness. Students at the civil engineering vocational high school will eventually be impacted by their career construction as a result of the social support they receive from their instructors, peers, and families. This study reinforces previous studies that showed that social support was positively related to career self-efficacy [21]. Empirically, social support does not directly affect strengthening career construction but must go through their career self-efficacy. The closest people who have an important influence on the individual need to encourage students' career choices and need to understand the career prospects for the individual. The higher the support obtained by students, the higher the ability of students to assess their potential, obtain career information, choose a career, and overcome problems related to their career choices.

This study also highlights career self-efficacy as an important factor that needs to be developed through the learning process at school. Teachers need to include in the curriculum related to strengthening aspects of career self-efficacy starting from planning, implementing, and evaluating students' career self-efficacy strengthening. Increasing the quality of instructional factors is not enough to shape students' career construction but also needs to involve parents in monitoring and supporting students' career choices. It is hoped that integrating the learning process and the social support monitoring program will strengthen the career construction formation of civil engineering vocational high school students. The findings of this study have consequences for those who work in vocational education, particularly those who construct career development programs for students at vocational high schools. Career development programs for vocational students must consider the suitability of students' areas of expertise so that students' confidence in their vocational abilities is higher. This helps them make career choice decisions when they graduate.

6. CONCLUSION

At vocational education, particularly in vocational schools, the career development of vocational students plays a crucial role. Studies on career construction have been highlighted because it is considered that building the strength of career plans for vocational students can help students strengthen their career plans. Therefore, a study to determine the factors forming career construction needs to be done. This study proves that career construction is directly influenced positively by career self-efficacy. Meanwhile, instructional quality and social support did not have a direct impact on career construction. Another conclusion is that the quality of students' educational and social support has a direct beneficial effect on their career self-efficacy. Finally, this study demonstrates that career self-efficacy serves as a mediator between instructional quality and social support in the career construction of civil engineering vocational high school students. The study's findings have important implications for vocational educators who want to construct career development or strengthening programs for their pupils.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. L. Savickas, "Career adaptability: An integrative construct for life-span, life-space theory," *The Career Development Quarterly*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 247–259, Mar. 1997, doi: 10.1002/j.2161-0045.1997.tb00469.x.
- [2] I. Šverko and T. Babarović, "Applying career construction model of adaptation to career transition in adolescence: A two-study paper," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 111, pp. 59–73, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.10.011.
- [3] W. C. Lu, "Future work-self salience and proactive career behavior among college student-athletes in Taiwan: A career construction model of adaptation," *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, vol. 27, p. 100259, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jhlste.2020.100259.
- [4] S. Santilli, L. Nota, and P. J. Hartung, "Efficacy of a group career construction intervention with early adolescent youth," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 111, pp. 49–58, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.06.007.
- [5] M. L. Savickas, E. J. Porfeli, T. L. Hilton, and S. Savickas, "The Student Career Construction Inventory," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 106, pp. 138–152, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.01.009.
- [6] F. Mutohari, S. Sutiman, M. Nurtanto, N. Kholifah, and A. Samsudin, "Difficulties in implementing 21st century skills competence in vocational education learning," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1229–1236, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v10i4.22028.
- [7] H. Zacher, C. W. Rudolph, T. Todorovic, and D. Ammann, "Academic career development: A review and research agenda," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 110, Part B, pp. 357–373, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.08.006.

- [8] Sudiyatno, M. Wu, A. Budiman, D. Purwantoro, T. Mahfud, and I. Siswanto, "The effect of instructional quality on vocational students' academic achievement and career optimism," *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 244–260, 2019.
- [9] V. L. Hariyanto, R. W. Daryono, N. Hidayat, S. H. Prayitno, and M. Nurtanto, "A framework for measuring the level of achievement of vocational students competency of architecture education," *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 157–171, 2022, doi: 10.3926/jotse.1188.
- [10] Sutiman, H. Sofyan, Soenarto, F. Mutohhari, and M. Nurtanto, "Students' career decision-making during online learning: The mediating roles of self-efficacy in vocational education," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1669–1682, 2022, doi: 10.12973/eu-jer.11.3.1669.
- [11] M. L. Savickas, "The theory and practice of career construction," in *Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work*, 2nd ed., Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc, 2013, pp. 147–183.
- [12] A. Hirschi, A. Herrmann, and A. C. Keller, "Career adaptivity, adaptability, and adapting: A conceptual and empirical investigation," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 87, pp. 1–10, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2014.11.008.
- [13] L. Indana, "Job absorption evaluation of graduates of computer and informatics engineering study program in Trenggalek Regency," (in Indonesian), Master Thesis, Yogyakarta State University, 2018.
- [14] T. Mahfud, I. Siswanto, D. S. Wijayanto, and P. F. Puspitasari, "Antecedent factors of vocational high school students' readiness for selecting careers: A case in Indonesia," *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 633–644, 2020, doi: 10.21831/cp.v39i3.32310.
- [15] J. Pfeffer, "Teaching power in ways that influence students' career success: some fundamental ideas," *Organizational Dynamics*, vol. 51, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.orgdyn.2021.100830.
- [16] O. C. Kahraman and D. D. Alrawadieh, "The impact of perceived education quality on tourism and hospitality students' career choice: The mediating effects of academic self-efficacy," *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, vol. 29, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jhlste.2021.100333.
- [17] R. W. Lent and S. D. Brown, "On conceptualizing and assessing social cognitive constructs in career research: A measurement guide," *Journal of Career Assessment*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 12–35, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1177/1069072705281364.
- [18] D. Spanjaard, T. Hall, and N. Stegemann, "Experiential learning: Helping students to become 'career-ready,'" *Australasian Marketing Journal*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 163–171, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ausmj.2018.04.003.
- [19] X. Tran, J. Williams, B. Mitre, V. Walker, and K. Carter, "Learning styles, motivation, and career choice: Insights for international business students from linguistic inquiry," *Journal of Teaching in International Business*, vol. 28, no. 3–4, pp. 153–167, 2017, doi: 10.1080/08975930.2017.1384949.
- [20] T. Mahfud, S. Indartono, I. N. Saputro, and I. Utari, "The effect of teaching quality on student career choice: The mediating role of student goal orientation," *Integration of Education*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 541–555, 2019, doi: 10.15507/1991-9468.097.023.201904.541-555.
- [21] C.-C. Chan, "The relationship among social support, career self-efficacy, career exploration, and career choices of Taiwanese college athletes," *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, vol. 22, pp. 105–109, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jhlste.2017.09.004.
- [22] C. Eesley and Y. Wang, "Social influence in career choice: Evidence from a randomized field experiment on entrepreneurial mentorship," *Research Policy*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 636–650, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.respol.2017.01.010.
- [23] P. C. Lee, S. (Tracy) Xu, and W. Yang, "Is career adaptability a double-edged sword? The impact of work social support and career adaptability on turnover intentions during the COVID-19 pandemic," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 94, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.102875.
- [24] Z. Zahed Zahedani, R. Rezaee, Z. Yazdani, S. Bagheri, and P. Nabeieci, "The influence of parenting style on academic achievement and career path," *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 130–134, 2016.
- [25] T. Mahfud, Y. Mulyani, R. Setyawati, and N. Kholifah, "The influence of teaching quality, social support, and career self-efficacy on the career adaptability skills: Evidence from a polytechnic in Indonesia," *Integration of Education*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 27–41, 2022, doi: 10.15507/1991-9468.106.026.202201.027-041.
- [26] T. Mahfud, B. K. Jati, and Y. Mulyani, "Soft skill competency map for the apprenticeship programme in the Indonesian balikan hospitality industry," *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 16–134, 2017.
- [27] K. Wehrle, M. Kira, and U.-C. Klehe, "Putting career construction into context: Career adaptability among refugees," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 111, pp. 107–124, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.08.007.
- [28] F. Zhu, Z. Cai, E. E. Buchtel, and Y. Guan, "Career construction in social exchange: a dual-path model linking career adaptability to turnover intention," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 112, pp. 282–293, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2019.04.003.
- [29] S. Billet, *Vocational education: Purpose, tradition and prospects*. New York: Springer Dordrecht, 2011.
- [30] S. Cohen and S. L. Syme, *Social support and health*. Orlando, FL: Academic Press, 1985.
- [31] S. Cohen, R. Mermelstein, T. Kamarck, and H. M. Hoberman, "Measuring the functional components of social support," in *Social Support: Theory, Research and Applications*, Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 1985, vol. 24, pp. 73–94.
- [32] H. C. Hung, "The influence of social support and career belief toward the career development of high school students of the department of physical education," *Journal of National Cheng Kung University Physical Education Research*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 17–33, 2012.
- [33] E. Isik, "Perceived social support and locus of control as the predictors of vocational outcome expectations," *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1426–1430, 2013, doi: 10.12738/estp.2013.3.1520.
- [34] M. E. Kenny, D. L. Blustein, A. Chaves, J. M. Grossman, and L. A. Gallagher, "The role of perceived barriers and relational support in the educational and vocational lives of urban high school students," *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 142–155, 2003, doi: 10.1037/0022-0167.50.2.142.
- [35] P. R. Garcia, S. L. D. Restubog, P. Bordia, S. Bordia, and R. E. O. Roxas, "Career optimism: The roles of contextual support and career decision-making self-efficacy," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 88, pp. 10–18, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2015.02.004.
- [36] M. E. Rogers, P. A. Creed, and A. Ian Glendon, "The role of personality in adolescent career planning and exploration: A social cognitive perspective," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 132–142, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2008.02.002.
- [37] B. McLennan, P. McIlveen, and H. N. Perera, "Pre-service teachers' self-efficacy mediates the relationship between career adaptability and career optimism," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 63, pp. 176–185, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.12.022.
- [38] H.-J. Niu, "Investigating the effects of self-efficacy on foodservice industry employees' career commitment," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 743–750, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2010.03.006.
- [39] K. M. Taylor and N. E. Betz, "Applications of self-efficacy theory to the understanding and treatment of career indecision," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 63–81, 1983, doi: 10.1016/0001-8791(83)90006-4.

- [40] C. F. Cheng, H. H. Tsai, and C. C. Kuo, "The construction of a career developmental counseling model for Taiwanese athletes," *Journal of Physical Education*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 443–464, 2016.
- [41] R. Lent, A. M. Lopez Jr., F. G. Lopez, and H.-B. Sheu, "Social cognitive career theory and the prediction of interests and choice goals in the computing disciplines," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 52–62, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2008.01.002.
- [42] Z. Wang and Y. Fu, "Social support, social comparison, and career adaptability: A moderated mediation model," *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 649–660, 2015, doi: 10.2224/sbp.2015.43.4.649.
- [43] S. Faraday, C. Overton, and S. Cooper, *Effective teaching and learning in vocational education*. London: LSN Learning, 2011.
- [44] W. Wagner, R. Göllner, A. Helmke, U. Trautwein, and O. Lüdtke, "Construct validity of student perceptions of instructional quality is high, but not perfect: Dimensionality and generalizability of domain-independent assessments," *Learning and Instruction*, vol. 28, pp. 1–11, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.learninstruc.2013.03.003.
- [45] E. B. Ray and K. I. Miller, "Social support, home/work stress, and burnout: Who can help?" *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 357–373, 1994, doi: 10.1177/0021886394303007.
- [46] N. E. Betz, K. L. Klein, and K. M. Taylor, "Evaluation of a short form of the Career Decision-Making Self-Efficacy Scale," *Journal of Career Assessment*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 47–57, 1996, doi: 10.1177/106907279600400103.
- [47] K. A. Bollen, *Structural equations with latent variable*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1989.
- [48] J. Hartono and W. Abdillah, *PLS (Partial Least Square) Concepts and Applications for Empirical Research*. Yogyakarta: BPFE (in Indonesian), 2009.
- [49] I. Ghozali and Fuad, *Structural Equation Modeling: Theory, Concepts, & Applications with the Lisrel 8.54 Program*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro (in Indonesian), 2008.
- [50] J. F. Hair, W. C. Black, B. J. Babin, and R. E. Anderson, *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*, 7th ed. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Prentice Hall, 2010.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Ida Nugroho Saputro is an Assistant Professor at the Building Engineering Education Department at the Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta. He received his doctoral at postgraduate of Technological and Vocational Education, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia. His research interest focuses on management in vocational education and training, workplace learning, teaching factory, vocational behavior, and career development. He has published the paper in Scopus indexed journal. He can be contacted at email: idanugroho@staff.uns.ac.id.

Soenarto is a Professor at Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia. His research interest focuses in vocational education and training, workplace learning, technical measurement, and research methodology. He has published the paper in Scopus indexed journal. He can be contacted at email: soenarto@uny.ac.id.

Herminarto Sofyan is a Professor at Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia. His main area of interest is the study of vocational education curriculum, employability skills, and collaboration between university and industry. He has published the paper in Scopus indexed journal. He can be contacted at email: hermin@uny.ac.id.